

“A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Planned Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Home Remedies Of Dysmenorrhea Among 12-15 Years Adolescent Girls In Selected School Or Jabalpur (M.P)”

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ABSTRACT

A central venous catheter (CVC), also known as a "central line," is a thin, flexible tube inserted into a large vein near the heart, typically in the neck, chest or groin, allowing for the administration of medications, fluids, blood products, or the drawing of blood samples. Distribution of adolescent girls total sample size was 60 with Convenient sample technique quantitative research approach with one group pre test and post test design was used.

Major Findings

Pre test - 29(48.3%) had inadequate knowledge, 22(36.7%) had moderately adequate knowledge and only 9(15%) had adequate knowledge on home remedies of dysmenorrhea Post test - (after PTP), 40(66.7%) had adequate knowledge, 18(30%) had moderately adequate knowledge and only 2(3.3%) had inadequate knowledge.

KEYWORDS - Knowledge, home remedies of dysmenorrhea, adolescent girls

INTRODUCTION

The term “adolescence” and “young people” are defined by World Health Organisation (WHO) as the age group 10-19 years and 10-24 years respectively. Adolescents comprise a significant part of today’s population. One in five persons is an adolescent aged 10 - 19 years, with 85% of adolescents living in developing countries. Young people make up over one quarter of the World’s population. More than half the World’s people are below 25 years of age and about a third is between 10 and 24 years of age. There are 1.2 billion adolescents and 1.7 billion young people in the World

OBJECTIVE

1. Assess pre - test Knowledge score among girls in selected higher secondary school at Jabalpur
2. Assess the post - test knowledge regarding home remedies of dysmenorrhea
3. Assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding home remedies of dysmenorrhea among girls in selected higher secondary school at Jabalpur.
4. Find out association between pre - test knowledge score with the selected demographical variables.

METHODOLOGY

Inclusion criteria

Adolescent school girls:

1. Who were between the age group of 12-15 years, and are studying in selected Nachiketa Senior Secondary School Vijay Nagar Jabalpur.

2. Who could read and write / English.

3. Who attained menarche.

4. Who were attending the class on the day of data collection.

Exclusion criteria

1. Those schools who did not give permission to do the study.

2. Girls who were not willing to participate in the study.

3. Those who were below 12 years of age.

DESCRIPTION OF TOOL

The instrument consists of selected demographic variables, gynecologic variables, knowledge questionnaire on home remedies of dysmenorrhea.

Part I: Demographic data and gynecologic data

Part II: Questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of adolescent school girls regarding Anatomy and physiology of female reproductive system, physiology of menstruation, dysmenorrhea and the interventions to control dysmenorrhea / menstrual distress.

SCORING CRITERIA

Scoring for the questionnaire was established based on the correct answers provided for each question. Each correct answer is fetched 1 mark and each incorrect or unanswered question fetched 0 marks. Participants can achieve a total score 30 out of 30 which can be the maximum 42

marks, available for the number of questions in the questionnaire. After participants complete the questionnaire, their scores were calculated by summing the marks earned answer.

S. NO.	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	SCORING
1.	POOR	0-10
2.	AVERAGE	11-20
3.	GOOD	21-30

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Section 1

Findings [Regarding the age group]: the majority of adolescent girls, 30(50%) of them were 12 years old, and 14(23.3%) were 13 years old, 12(20%) of them were in the age group of 14 years and 4(6.7%) of them were in 15 years old. Distribution of adolescents girls [education standard]: the majority of adolescent girls 30(50%) of them were in 7th standard and, 16(26.7%) were in 8th standard, 9(15%) were in 9th standard and 5(8.3%) were in 10th standard

Section 2

PRETEST KNOWLEDGE LEVEL

Level of knowledge	Pre test No. of respondents	%
POOR	29	48.3
AVERAGE	22	36.7

GOOD	9	15
Total	60	100

Section 3

POST TEST KNOWLEDGE LEVEL

No. of respondents (%)	%
2	3.3
18	30.0
40	66.7
60	100

Section 4

Pre-test knowledge mean was 11.92 with the standard deviation of 7.51 where as the post- test knowledge mean was 21.81 with the standard deviation of 5.56. The paired t- test was used to compare the pre and post knowledge. This reveals that, there is a highly significant improvement in the knowledge level in post test ($P < 0.05$). table value 2.00

Section 5

Association between the Pre - test Knowledge of girls regarding home remedies of dysmenorrhea with selected demographic variables. It deals with the association of pre-test knowledge score with demographic variables using the "chi-square" test for association.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted only in selected schools in south zone of Jabalpur (M.P).

The adolescent girls suffering from moderate to severe dysmenorrhea only were included in the study

CONCLUSION

The calculated "t" value of knowledge score was 6.25 at 3 degrees of freedom at 0.5.levels of significance which indicates the planned teaching programme was effective in

improving the knowledge regarding home remedies of dysmenorrhea. there was a significant association between pre-test knowledge with age, previously identified girls with dysmenorrhea.

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